

Original Research

Determinants of Mobile Banking Adoption in Tanzania: Evidence from NMB Mkononi Clients in Kongwa District

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Abstract

This investigation looks at the factors that affect the adoption of NMB Mkononi in the Kongwa district of Dodoma, Tanzania. A cross-sectional design method was employed, utilizing a three-stage sampling technique to select 154 participants systematically. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected through self-administered questionnaires and interviews. The Binary regression model was applied to elucidate the relationship between various factors and the adoption rate within the study area. The results showed that education level has a strong positive correlation ($p < 0.000$) with the adoption of NMB Mkononi, evidenced by an odds ratio of 62.94. This is because participants with a high level of education could have higher exposure to technology and thought to adopt it easily. Similarly, customers with high income levels and good network access have shown a significant positive ($p < 0.003$) relation toward adopting NMB Mkononi. Additionally, the findings indicated that younger users (ages between 18 and 35 years) are more likely to adopt the technology than older users. The study recommends that efforts to broaden the adoption base rendered by NMB Bank and policymakers should focus on enhancing technological features and addressing the various socioeconomic factors. The current study adds to and contributes to current literature on the understanding of the contribution of demographic variables (age, gender and education) on technological adoption in the context of less-developed countries like Tanzania.

Keywords: Adoption, determinants, mobile banking, Tanzania.

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Introduction

The swift progress in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has initiated a significant shift in financial institutions and banking services at the global level. One notable technological development is the emergence of the telephone and mobile phones (Hornuf *et al.*, 2024; Koi-Akrofi, 2022). Over the past decade, mobile phone usage and telecommunication networks have rapidly spread over the African continent. The growth of financial technology, particularly through mobile phones, has transformed the banking industry in Africa (Seck-Sarr, 2024; Sathvik, 2022). This progress has resulted in the introduction of mobile money banking services in most African countries (Mori and Mlambiti, 2020; Ngugi *et al.*, 2010). Research carried out by Shareef *et al.* (2018) and Sathvik (2022) projected that by 2019, 1.8 billion individuals across the globe would be utilizing mobile banking. Mobile money banking has compelled traditional African banks to adapt business practices and customer interactions (African Bankers Report, 2023; McKinsey & Company, 2022; Shareef *et al.*, 2018). Gu *et al.* (2009) noted that mobile money banking or financial services encompass activities such as peer-to-peer money transfers, bill and salary payments, and purchasing goods, all conducted without the need to visit conventional bank branches in person. Shankar & Jebarajakirthy (2019) further noted that this transformation has not only streamlined banking processes but has also enhanced the customer experience, resulting in increased expectations for improved digital services. This rise in digital participation has spurred the extensive acceptance of mobile banking, attracting global consumer interest due to its profound effects on the banking industry (McKinsey & Company, 2022; Nazaritehrani & Mashali, 2020).

The recent statistics on mobile phone usage show a significant increase in the adoption rate of mobile phones and other mobile devices across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) from 2013 to 2017 (Jaride and Taqi, 2021; Hassan and Wood, 2020). About half of the mobile money accounts in the year 2021 were reported to be in SSA out of the 1.35 billion mobile accounts around the globe (Seck-Sarr, 2024; GSMA report, 2023). An increase in the number of accounts opened in many African countries implies the continuous adoption of M-banking technology. Despite this increase, the report by World Bank's Global Findex indicated that more than two-thirds of adult populations in Sub-Saharan Africa have no access to formal financial services, presenting a 76% financial exclusion, mostly women, youth, and the poorest segments of society (Neves *et al.* 2023; Klapper & Demirguc-Kunt, 2021; Antunes *et al.*, 2021). Tanzania is part of SSA, and about 24% of its adult population is financially excluded from financial services, implying that they are not using the new technology introduced by financial or mobile money providers (FinScope Tanzania report, 2023). The increase in the number of the unsaved population segment indicates there are some obstacles to consider despite the reported increase in mobile adoption rate. These could include the low level of financial literacy, high cost of financial services and products, long physical distance to access point, and lack of mobile phones by some people (Avon *et al.*, 2023).

However, Swai (2015) defined Mobile banking adoption as the increase in several mobile phone and internet users in a particular area/region. On the other hand, Le *et al.* (2020) defined the concept of mobile banking as an Internet banking service using mobile devices (mobile phones) that allows customers to access and manage their financial services through financial and nonfinancial operations available and supported by

existing electronic channels like automated teller machines (ATMs), Internet banking services and customer call centers.

Research findings from studies like Koi-Akrofi (2022) and Hornuf et al. (2024) have shown that the expansion of mobile money services has been facilitated by the widespread adoption of mobile phones, which has revolutionized financial services in many African nations by incorporating large segments of the previously unbanked population. It is estimated that approximately 75% of online traffic in Africa is generated from mobile devices, prompting numerous banks to prioritize mobile banking over internet banking (Keya, 2024; African Bankers Report, 2023; Kato, 2019). Earlier predictions indicated that mobile money usage would continue to rise, with an expected reach of about 364 million users in Africa by 2012 (European Investment Bank, 2021; Reem & Jawdat, 2018). This upward trend in mobile money usage aligns with findings from Flototto et al. (2022), who anticipated a 10% annual increase in revenues from mobile financial services in Africa by 2025. The rapidly growing offerings were mainly from payment systems and electronic wallets. The convenience, accessibility, and improved features provided by mobile banking have transformed the relationship between customers and banks, empowering individuals to carry out various financial transactions with unparalleled ease and security (Nazaritehrani & Mashali, 2020). As mobile banking solutions continue to advance, they are set to reshape the banking industry, allowing financial institutions to address the continually changing demands of their clients.

Nevertheless, evidence from empirical research has shown that, even with the optimistic future outlook for mobile money financial services in SSA, the adoption rates for these services in the region remain low (Kiconco et al., 2018). Approximately 60% of adults still do not utilize mobile money banking or financial services in SSA (Athikho, 2023; Jaride and Taqi, 2021). This is further demonstrated by the fact that 90% of African monetary transactions are still conducted in cash, with only 7% carried out through digital or electronic channels (African Bankers Report, 2023; McKinsey and Company, 2022). The research conducted by Mas & Ng'weno (2021) revealed that countries like Kenya, which have seen success with mobile platforms such as M-PESA, lead in mobile payment adoption in the EAC, while other countries, like Tanzania, experience slower growth due to challenges in infrastructure and regulatory limitations. Various factors were mentioned to hinder the widespread adoption of mobile money services across the region, including Tanzania. The identified factors in the literature are perceived usefulness, ease of use, societal pressure, trust, relative advantages, facilitating conditions, and social-demographic factors (Asravor et al., 2021).

Tanzania has also experienced significant advancement in the mobile and telecommunications sector, with a large population segment benefiting. Numerous banks and financial institutions have adopted mobile banking technologies, which have diminished the service delivery time for their clients (Mwalwiba, 2020). This has led to notable growth in financial inclusion over the past two decades. According to the Financial Sector Deepening Trust (FSDT) report (2024) and FinScope Tanzania report (2023), 76% of adult Tanzanians accessed formal financial services in 2023. Despite this progress, a substantial portion of the population remains unconnected to formal banking services, creating an underbanked population that encounters some financial obstacles and restricted access to crucial financial services (Mwalwiba, 2020). However, very few

individuals residing in remote villages possess computers linked to the Internet, and the inadequate infrastructure does not support mobile banking (Rumanyika, 2015; Abdinoor & Mbamba, 2017). The lack of physical bank branches and services in underserved remote areas further intensifies financial exclusion, leaving many rural Tanzanians with limited prospects for obtaining their financial services in the future (Mori and Mlambiti, 2020; Mbilinyi et al., 2018).

In response to the imperative of fostering financial inclusion and addressing the unmet banking needs of remote communities, Tanzania has witnessed the emergence of major mobile networks that have rolled out mobile banking services with remarkable success. Notable among these mobile banking platforms are Tigo Pesa, M-Pesa, Halotel Money, and Airtel Money, which have strategically managed to bridge the gap in traditional bank coverage (Mwalwiba, 2020). These mobile banking services have proved instrumental in reaching underserved populations, particularly in rural and sparsely populated areas characterized by inadequate banking infrastructure (Anouze & Alamro, 2020; Mwalwiba, 2020). By leveraging the widespread usage of mobile phones, which have become ubiquitous across Tanzania, these mobile banking platforms offer a practical and accessible means to bring banking services closer to people's daily lives.

One of the key benefits of mobile banking is its ability to connect unbanked and underbanked populations to the national financial system. Tanzanian consumers can access various financial services through mobile banking, allowing them to engage with the formal financial sector without needing traditional bank accounts (Shaaban, 2020). According to Finscope Tanzania report (2023), financial inclusion increased from 65% in 2017 to 76% in 2023. This inclusive model empowers both individuals and businesses, stimulating economic development and narrowing financial access and opportunity gaps. Despite the significant rise in mobile banking users across Tanzania, a troubling gap remains between rural and urban populations regarding mobile banking adoption rates (Shau, 2021). While urban residents have widely embraced mobile banking, rural inhabitants, particularly those in Kongwa district, have not similarly engaged with this groundbreaking technology (Mori and Mlambiti, 2020; Shau, 2021). The Kongwa district, being rural-based, indicated the lowest rate of mobile money adoption (only 4.24%) in the region. This raises the question: Why this low rate, and what are the key factors contributing to this low adoption rate for NMB Mkononi in the district? Answers to these questions highlight the necessity for a comprehensive study on the factors that affect mobile banking acceptance among various demographic groups. Thus, this study is thought to explore the determinants of mobile banking technology adoption in the Kongwa district of Tanzania. Identifying the obstacles and motivators for adoption is vital for creating specific strategies that enhance financial inclusion and ensure that the advantages of mobile banking reach every segment of Tanzanian society.

Statement of the Problem

Mwalwiba (2020) and TCRA (2017) indicate that around 80% of Tanzania's population (mostly from urban areas), are utilizing e-banking services, with internet access reported at 40%. Commercial banks in Tanzania have started to launch their service using mobile phone channels integrated with seven big mobile phone operators, namely Vodacom, Airtel, Hallotel, and Yas by Mixx (Tigo). In light of this trend, NMB

Bank Plc launched its innovative service (NMB Mkononi) aimed to simplify money transfers between individuals. With the NMB Mkononi platform, customers can access convenient financial solutions, promote financial inclusion, minimize the necessity of traveling to banks, and enhance the efficiency of financial transactions.

Nevertheless, despite its potential advantages and user-friendliness, NMB Mkononi has encountered obstacles in achieving widespread usage, especially in Kongwa District. A report from NMB Bank Plc (2021) notes that the adoption of NMB Mkononi remains notably low in the Dodoma region, with Kongwa District recording the lowest adoption rate at only 4.24%, in contrast to other districts like Dodoma Urban (22.17%), Kondoa (16.05%), and Bahi (9%). The limited use of this service signifies that many residents in Kongwa are not fully utilizing NMB Mkononi to access vital financial services. When assessing the district's population alongside their financial requirements, the underutilization of NMB Mkononi raises important concerns and calls for an empirical investigation to uncover the underlying reasons for this discrepancy.

To enhance the adoption of e-banking solutions, the Tanzanian Government has initiated several measures to foster a supportive environment that encourages users to carry out electronic financial transactions with their devices (Magoma, 2019). These initiatives include policies aimed at decreasing transaction fees and ensuring the security and user-friendliness of online financial operations (Kato, 2019). Despite these initiatives, about 95% of individuals in Kongwa, particularly in rural areas, have not yet adopted the NMB Mkononi service, which might provide them with easier access to banking facilities (NMB Bank Plc, 2021). The continued low adoption rate of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa District (4.24%) raises essential questions such as why this low rate and that question needs empirical study to disclose the factors (including demographic characteristics) obstructing its acceptance and to identify areas for potential enhancements. A clear understanding of the key obstacles will predict the continuous future use of the technology by NMB customers as stipulated in the confirmation model (ECM) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Paramita and Cahyadi, 2024; Foroughi and Iranmanesh, 2019). That perceived use (PU) and perceived easy to use (PEU) complemented by satisfaction are the key determinants and form individual positive attitude and usage intention toward the use of mobile banking technology (Hornuf et al., 2024; Kumar et al., 2018).

Although some research, including that of Mori and Mlambiti (2020) and Swai (2015), has explored the influence of socioeconomic factors on the adoption of mobile banking in Tanzania, little attention was given to demographic characteristics and how these factors can influence the usage intention of an individual. Additionally, the findings from these studies have yielded inconsistent shreds of evidence. For instance, Mori and Mlambiti (2020) found no significant link between gender and age with the adoption of mobile banking technology. Conversely, research by Fall et al. (2020), Swai (2015), and Alafeef et al. (2011) demonstrated a negative and statistically significant relationship between demographic factors (like age and gender) and the adoption rates of mobile banking. These conflicting results regarding socioeconomic characteristics highlight the challenges in understanding fintech adoption in Tanzania. This situation calls for an in-depth study to enhance the comprehension of how socioeconomic characteristics impact the adoption of mobile banking technology. Thus, this study investigated the factors

influencing the adoption of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa district.

Therefore, the current study has concentrated on these factors that may impact the adoption of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa District. From the study findings, NMB Bank Plc and policymakers will be able to develop focused interventions and recommendations for boosting the adoption of NMB Mkononi and fostering financial inclusion among Kongwa residents and the country at large. These need to have a clear understanding of how customers' demographic characteristics affect the adoption of mobile banking. Results from this study have shown the relevance of socio-demographic characteristics such as age, education, and income in explaining the adoption of new technologies in the context of sub-Saharan Africa, especially in Tanzania.

Literature review

Theoretical Framework

This study utilized three theories in explaining the determinants of mobile banking technology adoption, namely the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the confirmation model (ECM), and the Theory of Adoption Technology (TAT). However, previous studies have proposed different theoretical frameworks for explaining technology adoption and users. Studies by Koi-Akrofi (2022), and Hornuf et al. (2024) applied the theory of TAM, Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DOI), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), and the Information System Success Model (ISSM) in explaining the factors influencing the adoption of technology. Evidence from these studies ascertains that the TAM fits in the context of financial technology in Sub-Saharan Africa to show how individual perceptions and attitudes toward technology can influence mobile banking adoption (Hornuf et al. 2024). This is because norms, attitudes, and customs are crucial determinants of individual behavioral intention and the use of technology (Tanveer et al., 2021; Mori and Mlambiti, 2020). Contrarily, Joo et al. (2018) reported that the application of TAM is limited only to pre-adoption behaviors in the technology use and fails to consider the continuance intention to use the Mobile-banking technology. To take care of the weakness, Foroughi et al. (2019) and Susanto et al. (2016) suggested the use of the combination of TAM and the Expectance-Confirmation Model (ECM) in elaborating both the pre-adoption and continuance intention to use the technology. This is because the determinants of pre-adoption are not the same as the post-adoption ones (Switbert & Baleche, 2022; Gilani et al., 2017).

In contrast to the TAM, the ECM focuses on factors that affect continuance intention (Bhattacharjee, 2001) and explains continuance intention in terms of perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEU), and satisfaction. Thus, previous studies have concluded that TAM can have an enhanced explanatory power when combined with other theories (Lee et al., 2003; Lin et al., 2012). Under this perspective, this study has used a combination of three theories, namely the TAM, ECM, and Theory of Adoption Technology (TAT). As noted by Abdinoor & Mbamba (2017), the adoption of mobile banking is not merely determined by technological features but also by other factors such as social and customer perceptions. This called for the inclusion of TAT due to its ability to consider factors beyond mere technological features, such as user attitudes and intentions, social influence, and facilitating conditions. Several studies, including those

of Hornuf et al. 2024, Alsokkar et al. 2023, Hammouri et al. 2021, and Foroughi et al. 2019, adopted the use of TAM in combination with ECM and TAT as the foundation to study the adoption and usage behavior of potential customers for mobile banking technology. The three theories were used in this study to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the pre and post-adoption behavior of NMB clients towards NMB Mkononi services in Kongwa District. A detailed explanation of the three theories is presented in the following section:

Theory of Technological Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Davis (1989) focuses on user acceptance of information systems (IS) and aims to identify behavioral intentions to utilize a system in the pre-adoption stage. The TAM mainly focuses on two critical factors that influence the acceptance of a system by potential users: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU). According to Davis *et al.* (1989) and Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), PEU and PU are two external parameters that encourage the clients' behavioral intention to rely on information systems. The perceived usefulness of technology is the extent to which people believe it helps them to accomplish essential tasks, and perceived ease of use refers to the extent to which a person believes that using a particular application would be effortless. It can be said that even if a technology is perceived as useful, it will only be used if it is perceived as easy to use and vice versa. Similarly, NMB Mkononi is a new technology, and its adoption will depend on how easy it is to use and the benefits associated. In the context of mobile banking adoption, TAM has demonstrated a high level of predictiveness regarding technology acceptance among potential users. It also agrees with the argument laid down by diffusion innovation theory (Shaikh et al., 2023; Rogers, 2010). An older adult's perception of digital games could be either challenging and wasteful or as providing valuable mental stimulation and easy to learn will significantly influence their willingness to adopt this technology.

However, TAM has been reported by Foroughi et al. (2019) and Joo et al. (2018) to have shortfalls in failing to explain the post-adoption behavior of the potential of the technology use. To get a comprehensive understanding of the determinants of technology adoption, such as Mobile Money, Foroughi et al. (2019) recommended a combination of TAM with other theories, such as ECM and TAT. Though TAM has faced these criticisms, it remains a valuable framework and has been applied in numerous investigations to understand the factors influencing the intention of older adults to embrace new technologies (Braun, 2013).

The relevance of the Theory of Technological Acceptance, proposed by Davis (1989), to this research, lies in its ability to focus on understanding the behavioral patterns of individuals, particularly those residing in Kongwa district in Dodoma region, in accepting and comprehending the system used to operate NMB Mobile service. This theory allowed the study to explore how perceived usefulness and ease of use influence individuals' intentions to engage in financial transactions through NMB Mkononi for their daily activities.

Expectance-Confirmation Model (ECM)

Choi et al. (2019) and Gong et al. (2018) utilized the ECM in their research to investigate the adoption behavior of clients regarding mobile banking in SSA. Additionally, Gilani et al. (2017) observed that the ECM is now frequently applied to understand individuals' attitudes toward the sustained use of Information Systems (IS). This theory emphasizes the elements that affect continuance and retention, as long-term usage is influenced by ongoing use rather than just initial usage (Alraimi et al., 2015; Ambalov, 2018; Wang et al., 2019). According to Bhattacherjee (2001), the ECM centers on the elements that influence continuance intention and describes this intention as perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEU), and satisfaction. The ECM ascertains that the extent to which the customer's expectations are met with a given product is directly influenced by the level of satisfaction (Abdullah et al., 2024; Al-Gasawneh et al., 2022a). This implies that the level of satisfaction obtained by consumers of the product or service increases when their expectations are met. Additionally, users' intention to continue using is shaped not only by their perceptions and satisfaction but also by the attitudes of the users toward the product or services. Research conducted by Kumar et al. (2018) demonstrated that the Expectation-Confirmation Model (ECM) was developed based on existing literature regarding client behavior, and it was subsequently connected to both empirical and theoretical findings from earlier studies on Information Systems (IS) usage to create a novel model for understanding IS continuance. Thus, the model confirms that, in order for customers to be able to validate their expectations on the product quality, they should also have a positive experience (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2023a; Hammouri et al., 2022). The model further illustrates that users' intention to continue using an IS can be determined by their satisfaction with the perceived usefulness (PU) of continued IS usage and their actual usage of the system. Similarly, potential customers of mobile banking in Kongwa district will continue to use the NMB Mkononi innovation only if they are satisfied with the technology. Moreover, the users' satisfaction is significantly influenced by expectations regarding prior PU and IS use confirmation. Unlike the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the ECM focuses on the elements that affect consistency and retention, operating under the belief that the enduring success and sustainability of an IS are contingent upon continued usage instead of merely initial adoption (Wang et al., 2019).

Technology Adoption Theory

The Technology Adoption Theory (TAT) was proposed by Carr (1999) as a comprehensive framework for understanding how customers behave and feel toward technology adoption. This theory suggests that the decision to adopt technology is influenced by different factors, not just its technical features; it encompasses user attitudes, personality traits, social influences, trust, and various supportive conditions. According to Carr (1999), technology adoption is defined as the phase in which individuals or organizations choose a technology. In a time marked by swift technological progress across various fields, the issue of technology adoption has acquired considerable importance. Organizations and governments dedicate significant resources to introducing innovative technologies that have the potential to transform users' lives. Nonetheless, as pointed out by Choudrie and Dwivedi (2005), such financial commitments may produce limited outcomes if the innovations are not accepted by the users they target. The ability

of TAT to take into account factors beyond just the technical characteristics, including user attitudes and intentions, social influences, and supportive conditions, has led to its use in this study (Abdinoor & Mbamba, 2017). The present research seeks to reveal an in-depth understanding of the factors that encourage or obstruct people from using mobile banking services in the area under study. More precisely, it concentrates on determining the factors influencing the adoption of NMB Mkononi by user customers in Kongwa District, located in the Dodoma region.

The theoretical foundations of TAM, ECM, and TAT provide important frameworks for exploring the factors that affect the acceptance of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa District. This study, therefore, aims to clarify the complex interactions that shape individuals' choices to use mobile banking services, thereby enhancing the understanding of technology adoption within the financial sector.

Empirical Literature Review

Factors Influencing e-banking Adoption and Customer Perceptions

Empirical evidence from prior research highlighted various reasons why individuals choose to adopt and utilize a particular technology, suggesting that a mix of theories might effectively explain this phenomenon. Jaride and Taqi (2021) in their study of exploring factors affecting mobile banking adoption identified trust, social influence, performance expectancy, behavioral intention, and facilitating conditions as the primary determinants. Similarly, Abdinoor & Mbamba (2017) emphasized that customers' perceptions and attitudes towards several service dimensions, including quality, security, accessibility, performance, social influence, affordability, convenience, price, comparative advantage, and associated risks, can significantly impact the adoption of mobile banking technology. Conversely, Ndekwa et al. (2018) pointed out that social pressure, attitudes, and facilitating conditions were key influences on students' intentions to embrace mobile money.

Switbert and Baleche (2022) examined the factors prompting commercial banks in Tanzania to implement e-banking and assessed customer perceptions. The research underscored several essential drivers for e-banking adoption, such as customer satisfaction, perceived convenience, time efficiency, usefulness, and ease of use. Customers recognized the advantages of e-banking, including the capability to perform transactions easily and effectively. They valued the time-saving features of digital banking, which enabled them to oversee their finances from their devices. The perceived utility of e-banking services also played a role in its acceptance, as customers acknowledged the convenience it added to their everyday financial tasks.

Nonetheless, despite the favorable aspects of e-banking, the findings indicated that consumers were concerned about the security of these services. This apprehension regarding potential cyber risks and unauthorized access to their accounts deterred some individuals from fully adopting e-banking. Moreover, customers experienced difficulties related to network issues, which impacted the reliability of digital banking services. High transaction fees were another element that affected customer opinions, leading to some dissatisfaction with the expenses associated with using e-banking platforms.

Kibanda (2020) researched the elements influencing the acceptance of mobile banking in Tanzania. While the study did not specifically target the adoption of NMB Mkononi, it offered important insights into the necessity of investing in mobile banking and IT innovations to facilitate effective service delivery and increase mobile banking adoption. The research underscored the importance of mobile banking services as a crucial means of reaching customers in remote and underserved areas. Mobile banking provided a chance to connect traditional banking services with individuals lacking access to formal financial institutions. The study pointed out the opportunity for mobile banking to drastically improve financial inclusion and alter methods by which individuals carry out transactions. Banks could draw a broader customer base and improve service delivery efficiency if resources were dedicated to mobile banking infrastructure and user-friendly application improvements. The results advocated for a technology-driven banking services adoption strategy to enhance customer experiences and broaden access to financial services for diverse population segments.

Factors leading to the adoption of e-banking

Poon (2008) carried out a research study in Malaysia to explore the factors that promote the adoption of e-banking in commercial banks. The research identified several elements that affected customers' choices to embrace e-banking services in Africa. The presence of essential devices like smartphones and computers significantly facilitated customers' ability to access and utilize e-banking platforms. Customer contentment with e-banking advantages, such as convenience and time-saving features, also played a role in the adoption process. The study underscored the influence of competition on e-banking adoption. When customers assessed the services offered by various banks, they were more inclined to select banks that provided user-friendly and effective e-banking solutions.

Koi-Akrofi (2022) evaluated 20 journal articles regarding the adoption of mobile technology, revealing that both external and internal factors affected the acceptance of mobile money services. This indicates that an individual's intention to adopt any new technology is not solely dependent on the technology itself but is also shaped by their perceptions influenced by social norms and attitudes (Azjen, 1991; Foroughi and Iranmanesh, 2019). The perceived ease of use and usefulness emerged as crucial factors in customer adoption. This is because users favor platforms that are user-friendly and provide clear benefits for their financial management. In agreement with this, Hornuf et al. (2024) found that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness positively impacted mobile money adoption across most sub-Saharan African countries. Likewise, Firmansyah et al. (2023) discovered that trust and security were vital components affecting the adoption of e-banking, as customers sought reassurance that their financial data would remain secure and that transactions would be safe. According to Shaikh and Karjaluo (2015), mobile banking provides four access methods for customers: downloadable mobile applications for smartphones, web browsers operable on mobile devices, downloadable apps for tablets, and short messaging services (SMS) that deliver account information notifications. Additionally, factors such as customers' level of education and income influenced their likelihood of adopting e-banking services, as reported in the study by Mori and Mlambiti (2020) in Tanzania. Customers with high education and income were reported to adopt mobile banking technology easily in countries like Tanzania. Furthermore, evidence from current empirical studies like those

by Mori and Mlambiti (2020), Asravor et al., (2021), Mandi (2022), Flototto *et al.* (2022), and Yohana *et al.* (2024) indicate that mobile banking in Tanzania is at a lower rate compared to other countries in EAC. The major factors contributing to the low adoption rate included lack of Agent networks, poor customer support, lack of enough cash among agents, poor network accessibility and coverage, and lack of awareness on the part of consumers.

Although some research, including that of Mori and Mlambiti (2020) and Swai (2015), has explored the socioeconomic factors that influence the adoption of mobile banking in Tanzania, the findings from these studies have yielded inconsistent evidence. For instance, Mori and Mlambiti (2020) found no significant link between gender and age concerning the adoption of mobile banking technology. Conversely, research by Fall et al. (2020), Swai (2015), and Alafeef et al. (2011) demonstrated a negative and statistically significant relationship between demographic factors (like age and gender) and the adoption rates of mobile banking. These conflicting results regarding socioeconomic characteristics highlight the challenges in understanding fintech adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa, including Tanzania. This situation highlights the need for an in-depth study to enhance the comprehension of how socioeconomic characteristics impact the adoption of mobile banking technology.

Research Methods

Research Approach and Design

The study employed a mixed research approach and a cross-sectional design that involved data collection from participants in a single period. This cross-sectional approach was particularly effective for efficiently addressing the research aims and offering prompt insights into the factors that affect the adoption of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa district, Dodoma. The method facilitated comparisons among different participant groups based on a range of demographic and technological variables, providing a wide framework for analysis. The cross-sectional format was cost-effective, effectively tackling the research questions without requiring long-term tracking. This design has also been utilized in studies such as those by Mashenene et al. (2024), Magasi et al. (2020) and Mori and Mlambiti (2020). Adopting this research approach, enabled the study to illuminate the factors driving the adoption of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa district, contributing to a thorough understanding of e-banking acceptance in the area.

Data Collection Tools and Study Area

Data was gathered using structured questionnaires distributed to evaluate the participants' awareness of e-banking technologies as well as the factors influencing the adoption of NMB Mkononi services. The questionnaires contained structured questions that were self-administered to the respondents in the study area since it was easy for respondents to choose the answer that best described their situation. Participants were asked about their awareness of the NMB Mkononi technology, previous use of mobile banking technology, usefulness of the technology, their demographic characteristics, and their expectation on the use of NMB Mkononi. On average, the participants spent 15 minutes completing the survey. Furthermore, qualitative data was obtained through

interviews with NMB officers and district leaders to gain a more profound contextual insight into the determinants for NMB Mkononi adoption. Additional, secondary data was sourced from document reviews, which included an analysis of written materials such as government publications, online articles, annual reports from NMB Bank Plc, and documents and checklists related to NMB Mkononi.

The research was conducted in Kongwa District, situated in the eastern part of the Dodoma Region in Tanzania. Kongwa District was chosen for the study due to its relevance in terms of low NMB Mkononi adoption. NMB Bank is the largest financial institution in Tanzania, with 139 branch networks nationwide (NMB Bank Plc Report, 2021). Despite the launch of the NMB Mkononi service by NMB Bank Plc, this district showed the lowest adoption rate, with an approximate average of 479 individuals or customers utilizing the service (NMB Bank Plc Report, 2021). This low adoption rate in Kongwa District sharply contrasted with other districts in Dodoma, such as Dodoma Urban (22.17%), Kondoa (16.05%), and Bahi (9%), which reported considerably higher percentages of NMB Mkononi users. The reasons for selecting Kongwa District as the focus of this study were varied and significant. Firstly, the district's minimal use of the NMB Mkononi service highlighted a critical obstacle in financial inclusion initiatives. Secondly, Kongwa district is among the selected strategic rural-based branches in the customer base expansion for NMB Mkononi by the Bank. As a region with limited banking services, Kongwa District stood to gain substantial benefits from the convenience and accessibility provided by mobile banking solutions like NMB Mkononi. Therefore, it was essential to understand the factors that affect the adoption of NMB Mkononi in this particular district to develop targeted strategies that enhance financial inclusion and increase overall banking accessibility for the local community.

Validity and Reliability Tests

Before carrying out the data collection exercise, a pilot study was conducted with 10% of the participants to guarantee that all questionnaire items were properly defined and had the same meaning for all participants. On the other hand, the reliability of research instruments was tested using the Cronbach Alpha, where all variables scored the value of 0.7 and above. This indicated that the variables selected were suitable and reliable for the study to generate the information (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2006).

Table 1. Reliability test

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
Gender	2	0.731
Education level	4	0.861
Income level	2	0.801
Network Stability	2	0.721

Sampling Procedures and Techniques

This research utilized a three-stage multi-stage sampling technique to guarantee a representative group of participants from Kongwa District, Dodoma. This procedure included multiple steps for selecting participants for the data collection process. The target population comprised potential users of NMB Mkononi and individuals who had not embraced the service. Participants from various age ranges, educational levels, genders, and experiences with technology were included in the sample to complement the diversity. The participants were selected based on the number of users, distance from the Kongwa NMB branch, number of NMB customers, and accessibility of the area. The stages were classified based on the local government administrative demarcation. Administratively, Kongwa district had 22 wards located in a scattered manner. Based on this, three levels of selection were made at the ward, village, and household levels.

In the first stage, clusters or wards within Kongwa District were purposefully chosen based on the number of NMB Mkononi users identified from the NMB Kongwa branch. All twenty-two (22) wards in the Kongwa district were included in this selection. This step was designed to capture different areas within the district and ensure a wide-ranging representation of participants. The ward and village list provided by local authorities was used as the sampling frame for this phase. In the second stage, one village from each ward was purposely selected based on the number of NMB Mkononi users, resulting in 22 villages in total.

In the third stage, seven (7) households were chosen from each village using systematic random sampling for each selected village. In each village, every " k^{th} " household was selected, where " k " represents the sampling interval calculated based on the total number of households in the village obtained from local authorities and the desired sample size. From the selected households, individuals who were NMB Mkononi users were identified through interviews or questionnaires, asking participants about their usage of the NMB Mkononi service. This step helped to distinguish between the adopted and non-adopted users of the mobile banking service in the district. A total of 154 participants from the 22 villages, involving both NMB Mkononi users and non-users in Kongwa District, were selected and included in the sample size. According to Saunders et al. (2012), a sample of 30 respondents is statistically significant and enough to conclude. Thus, the sample of 154 was considered adequate and significant statistically in concluding the effects of determinants for NMB Mkononi adoption in Kongwa district.

Data analysis and analytical model selection

Both descriptive and inferential statistics analysis were used in the study, and the relationship between the dependent and independent variables was examined using binary logit regression analysis. The demographic characteristics of the respondents were examined using descriptive analysis, which provided information on the distribution and properties of the variables. Additionally, the qualitative information obtained from the key informants who were purposefully selected was also examined using content analysis.

Table 2. Operationalization and measurement of variables

Variable	Variable Type	Indicator	Measurement
Determinants	Independent	Gender of respondent	Binary (1= Male. 2= female)
		Education Level	Level of Education attained
		Income Level	Monthly income in TZS
		Network Stability	Binary (1= Stable, 2= Not Stable)
NMB Mkononi	Dependent	Uses	Binary (adopted 2= not adopted)

On the other hand, binary logistic regression analysis was employed in assessing the factors influencing the adoption of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa district. The model was selected because the dependent variable (Adoption of NMB Mkononi) was binary (1= Adopt, 2=Not adopt), presenting latent information as adopt or not adopt. Binary logistic as a utility model fits well in the analysis of latent variables like the adoption of technology, which have two outcomes. This statistical method allowed the study to examine the relationship between the adoption of NMB Mkononi and various independent variables.

$$P (Y= 1/X) = \beta_0 +\beta_1X_1+\beta_2X_2+\beta_3X_3+\beta_4X_4 +\beta_5X_5 + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where;

Y= Dependent variable (NMB Mkononi service/product)

β_0 =Intercept, X1 = Age, X2 = Education, X3 = Marital status,

X4 = Income level per month, X5 = Network stability and ε = Error

Ethical Considerations

Approval from relevant authorities (Districts and NMB bank managements) was obtained to ensure compliance with ethical standards and guidelines. Voluntary participation and confidentiality were the priorities of this study. Transparency, accuracy, and the avoidance of harm were ensured, and any potential conflicts of interest were disclosed to maintain objectivity.

Results and Discussion

Reliability and Model Fitness

Before carrying out the Binary analysis, we tested the appropriateness of the model (Binary Logistics Regression) using the KMO measures to ensure the properness of the variables. The results in Table 3 show that the value of KMO is 0.786, indicating the appropriateness of data for factor analysis and use of the model. The high significance in Bartlett's test ($p <0.000$) implies the existence of the link between variables analyzed in

this study and, therefore, signifies the proper factor analysis approach (Hair *et al.*, 2016; Mashenene *et al.*, 2024).

Table 3. Results on KMO and Bartlett's Tests

Kaiser- Meyer-Olkin Sampling Adequacy Measure (KMO)	0.786	
Bartlett's Sphericity test	Approx. Chi-Square	15.300
	df	154
	Sig	0.000

Descriptive Results on Demographic Characteristics

Based on the results shown in Table 4, male representation was marginally higher (56.5%) than female representation (43.5%). The participants' gender representation is adequately balanced in this distribution, which is crucial for guaranteeing a representative and diverse sample. Male and female participants in the study were fairly evenly distributed (56.5% male, 43.5% female), suggesting that both sexes are investigating online banking options such as NMB Mkononi. The adoption of NMB Mkononi may be significantly influenced by gender. It's crucial to remember that gender may interact with other variables, such as socioeconomic status and cultural norms, to affect the adoption choice. Mashenene *et al.* (2024) reported similar findings, showing male respondents outnumbered female respondents in Tanzania. Consequently, gender disparities were connected to the adoption choice and need more research.

Table 4. Demographic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Sex		
Male	87	56.5
Female	67	43.5
Marital Status		
Single	56	36.4
Marriage	89	57.8
Divorced	9	5.8
Education Level		
No formal Education	46	29.9
Primary education	54	35.1
Secondary education	34	22.1
College/University Education	20	13.0
Awareness of the service		
Awareness of the service	59	38.3
Un-aware	95	61.7

Marital Status

Results in Table 4 further show that the majority of respondents were married (57.8%), followed by single individuals (36.4%), and a smaller percentage were divorced (5.8%). This distribution highlights the diverse marital statuses of the participants and provides a glimpse into the potential influence of marital status on the adoption of NMB Mkononi. Marital status appears to have some influence on the adoption of NMB Mkononi. Married participants (57.8%) form the largest group, which could be attributed to shared financial responsibilities and the convenience of digital banking for managing joint finances. Conversely, the adoption seems to be different for single individuals (36.4%) and those who are divorced (5.8%). Single individuals might prioritize personal financial management, while divorced participants may have unique financial needs and perceptions.

Education Level

Participants' educational backgrounds were also varied, ranging from informal education to college/university education. The largest portion of participants had completed primary education (35.1%), followed by those with no formal education (29.9%), secondary education (22.1%), and college/university education (13.0%). This distribution underscores the importance of considering participants' educational levels as a potential factor in influencing their adoption of digital banking services. The diversity in education levels among the respondents introduces an interesting dimension to the analysis. Participants with no formal education (29.9%) and those with primary education (35.1%) might have varying degrees of digital literacy and comfort with technology, making them delay in adoption. On the other hand, participants with secondary education (22.1%) and college/university education (13.0%) could have higher exposure to technology and thought to adopt it easily. The results support those of Mori and Mlambiti (2020), who found that customers with higher education levels were more likely to adopt mobile banking in Arusha, Tanzania. In this regard, education could be a determining factor in understanding the ease of use and perceived benefits of NMB Mkononi. Similar observations are found in the TAM and ECM that the ease and usefulness of the technology facilitate its adoption. Offering user-friendly features and education could bridge potential gaps among different education levels.

Awareness of the Service

Among the participants, 38.3% were aware of the NMB Mkononi service's existence, while 61.7% were unaware. This division presents valuable insight into the extent to which the service's awareness has penetrated the study area. The disparity between participants who were aware of the NMB Mkononi service (38.3%) and those who were not (61.7%) is noteworthy. This suggests that while the service has made some inroads in awareness, there is still significant room for growth in the banking industry. The low level of awareness among NMB Mkononi customers could be due to various factors, including limited marketing efforts, inadequate communication channels, or unfamiliarity with digital banking. Similar results were obtained by Odoyo et al. (2016), who found that lack of awareness and language barriers were the other factors influencing mobile money service adoption among customers in Kenya. Therefore, enhancing awareness campaigns

and education about the service's benefits could be instrumental in increasing adoption rates.

Level of E-Banking Technology Awareness in the Study Area

The study also wanted to understand how aware the NMB clients are of the availability of E-banking services in the Kongwa district. We constructed various question statements to test the awareness of the client, and responses are presented in the following section.

Awareness and usage of E-banking Services:

The results in Table 5 indicated a significant level of awareness regarding e-banking services among the respondents. The majority of participants (88.3%) reported that they had heard of the availability of e-banking services, suggesting that digital banking concepts have reached a substantial portion of the population. The awareness of e-banking services among NMB clients highlights the growing penetration of digital financial solutions in the region. For instance, respondents may be familiar with popular mobile money services like Tigo Pesa, M-Pesa, and Halo-Pesa, which have become integral to daily transactions for many. These services enable users to transfer money, pay bills, and make purchases using their mobile phones. This awareness could be attributed to various factors, including increased connectivity, improved information dissemination, and growing familiarity with technological advancements.

The data (Table 5) also reveals that a considerable proportion of respondents (82.5%) have used e-banking services. This suggests a notable level of acceptance and adoption of digital banking practices among the surveyed population. The fact that more respondents have used e-banking services compared to those who have only heard of them implies a positive trend in the adoption of digital financial tools.

Table 5. Level of E-banking Technology Awareness

Statement	Yes		No	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Ever heard of any E-banking service	136	88.3	18	11.7
Ever used any E-banking service	127	82.5	27	17.5
Ever heard of NMB Mkononi's service	59	38.3	95	61.7
Ever used NMB Mkononi's service	33	21.4	121	78.6
Do you have a mobile phone	93	60.4	61	39.6
Do you have a smartphone	14	9.1	140	90.9
Do you know where the NMB offices are located	48	31.2	106	68.8
Are the NMB agents near where you live	22	14.3	132	85.7

Awareness and Usage of NMB Mkononi:

Regarding NMB Mkononi service, the awareness and usage levels are slightly lower. About 38.3% of respondents reported having heard of NMB Mkononi, and only 21.4% have used it. This indicates that, although the overall e-banking awareness is high (82%),

the awareness and usage percentages of NMB Mkononi are comparatively lower. This presents an opportunity for NMB Bank to enhance its marketing strategies and outreach efforts to improve its digital banking service awareness and adoption rates. Similarly, individuals might be aware of e-banking services in general but might not have explored NMB Mkononi due to factors like branding, features, or trust in the provider. This concurs with the argument presented by Hornuf et al. (2024) that low levels of digital and financial literacy represent a significant barrier to achieving full financial inclusion.

Mobile Phone Ownership and Smartphone Usage

The ownership of mobile phones by 60.4% of respondents is significant and underscores the role of mobile technology in financial inclusion. The majority of respondents had basic phones that did not support the use of NMB Mkononi. However, smartphone ownership and usage are relatively lower (9.1%), suggesting that a significant portion of the population uses basic mobile phones. This information is crucial for designing user-friendly interfaces that cater to a diverse range of devices. The study findings were supported by results from interviews of Key informants that; *The economic situation is very low here, with many being small-scale farmers and herders. Some don't even see the importance of owning a mobile phone. That's why you'll find that most people don't own phones*" (Makawa WEO, 2023)

Accessibility to NMB Offices and Agent Proximity

The lower percentage (31.2%) of respondents who know the locations of NMB offices might be the reason why some individuals face challenges in physically accessing banking facilities. This highlights the potential challenge in physical accessibility to NMB services for a significant portion of the population, which could impact their adoption decisions. Similarly, the limited proximity of NMB agents to respondents' residences (14.3%) could be compared to having medical clinics available but not necessarily close by. This highlights the significance of bringing banking services closer to individuals, particularly in areas of limited physical access. Mageesse (2019) disclosed the limitations of access to NMB offices for some customers in Dar es Salaam, which is similar to these findings.

Factors Influencing the Adoption of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa District

Results in Table 6 present a positive statistical relationship ($p = .009$) between the male clients and NMB Mkononi indicated by a coefficient of 0.767 and adoption odds of 2.27. This suggests that male clients are two times more likely to adopt the NMB Mkononi service than females. This can be explained by the fact that males are more willing to take risks as compared to women (Veronica et al., 2022; Alafeef et al., 2011), so it will be easy for them to try new technology like NMB Mkononi. Additionally, based on cultural traditions and norms that empower more males as heads of household in Tanzania, this gives male customers more access to resources such as income, which gives them the ability to own smartphones. Similar results were reported by Mori and Mlambiti (2020) that male customers were positively associated with the adoption of mobile banking in Tanzania. Different from male clients, women are limited from accessing more resources, thus, it becomes difficult for them to own smartphones, which is the right device for using

NMB Mkononi. Results are consistent with Venkatesh and Morris (2000), who found that gender is an important determinant of technology adoption and usage in Germany and the UK, in that males are more likely than females to adopt new technology. Contrary to those of DeBaillon and Rockwell (2005), who found an insignificant relationship between gender and the adoption of Internet banking. The results are also in line with the TAT arguments that social influences and supportive conditions for the user of technology could increase the adoption rate (Abdinooor & Mbamba, 2017). In Kongwa district, male customers were culturally and financially empowered as compared to females, a situation which enabled them to access and own smart phones, the best tool for using NMB Mkononi.

Table 6. The Factors Influencing the Adoption of NMB Mkononi in Kongwa District

Socio-economic Characteristics	Coeff	St. Err.	Sig.	Odd Ratio
Gender (1=Male, 2=Female)	.767	0.188	0.009	2.275
Age (1=Above 35yrs, 0 = Below 35yrs)	-.217	0.945	0.164	0.935
Education level (1= Secondary/College 2= Primary school)	.478	50.82	0.000	62.94
Marital Status (1=Married,0= Otherwise)	.546	0.943	0.681	1.337
Income level (TSH)	.679	0.715	0.003	2. 540
Network Stability (1=Stable, 0= others)	.234	0.743	0.015	1.445
Constant	.521	0.881	0.002	
R ² (Cox and Snell)	0.56			

The level of education (Table 6) has been shown to have a strong positive correlation with the adoption of NMB Mkononi, evidenced by an odds ratio of 62.94. This indicates that individuals with secondary education or higher are 63 times more likely to adopt NMB Mkononi compared to those with primary education or less. This finding is extremely statistically significant ($p < 0.000$), highlighting that educational attainment significantly influences the adoption of new technologies. Higher education equips clients with the knowledge to adapt to new technology easily. Additionally, education enhances access to information regarding the advantages and use of mobile banking technology, particularly its accessibility and user-friendliness. These findings are consistent with those of Shaikh et al. (2023), Burgess (1986), and Munisi (2015), who suggested that individuals with higher education are nearer to adopting new technologies than those with lower levels of education. Similarly, the study by Sulaiman et al. (2007) revealed that 75% of mobile banking adaptors had higher education, giving them more confidence and exposure to using mobile banking services than their counterparts. The results are also supported by arguments laid down by TAM and ECM theories that adopting a new technology is based on the customer's perception of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use technology. All these findings confirm that education is a crucial determinant affecting the uptake of newly introduced mobile banking technology.

Income has also emerged as a significant factor in adopting NMB Mkononi technology, as indicated by a statistically significant positive relationship with adoption attitudes. An odds ratio of 2.54 relating to income suggests that higher-income consumers are three times more likely to adopt this new technology than their lower-income

counterparts. The results further imply that an increase in income is associated with a greater likelihood of adopting mobile banking technology as it empowers people to own and use smartphones. Studies by Mori and Mlambiti (2020) and Krogh et al. (2009) supported similar conclusions. Since utilizing NMB Mkononi necessitates modern devices like smartphones, individuals with higher incomes have a greater ability to buy and own these devices in comparison to those with lower incomes. Research shows that affluent customers are more likely to use their smartphones to transfer money between their bank accounts and mobile devices, making various purchases. This argument accords with that described by ECM that the adoption and continued usage of a new technology like mobile banking does not only depend on its technological merits but also other facilitating conditions such as income and education.

The results presented in Table 4 demonstrate that network stability positively influenced the adoption rates among clients of NMB Mkononi in the study region. The positive coefficient of 0.679 and an odds ratio of 2.54 for network stability suggest that clients were three times more likely to use NMB Mkononi services in areas with stable networks. This is because the effectiveness and efficiency of mobile banking largely depend on the reliability and stability of Internet connectivity. In addition, it was observed that charges for transferring funds from a bank to mobile vary significantly from one network provider to another while transacting from the same bank account (Shau, 2021). These findings align with those of Masrek et al. (2014) and Jaride and Taqi (2021), who noted that customers are more likely to engage with technologies if they perceive them as reliable and accessible. In such circumstances, they are more inclined to evaluate all services positively and thus enhance user satisfaction.

The age of respondents indicates a negative relation with the adoption of NMB Mkononi technology and is not statistically significant ($p = 0.164$). Similar to that of Mirza *et al.* (2009), who found that age does not have a prominent influence on the adoption of mobile banking services, especially the Internet. However, the negative coefficient of 0.217 suggests that age is still an important factor for adopting the new technology. The odds ratio of 0.935 indicates that for each unit increase in age, the odds of adopting NMB Mkononi decrease by a factor of 0.935. This implies that older clients are less likely to adopt the NMB Mkononi services than youths. As noted by Alafeef et al. (2011), the majority of potential users of mobile banking in Jordan are between 17 and 35 years old because they are familiar with the latest mobile technologies. Married individuals are 1.3 times more likely to adopt NMB Mkononi compared to those who are single. However, this result is not statistically significant ($p = 0.692$). Despite the insignificance of marital status, yet presents the noted influence on the adoption of technology. The results from age are also supported by the demonstration from the TAM that the PEU and PU are two external parameters that encourage the clients' behavioral intention to use introduced new technology. Thus, an older client could perceive difficulty in using technology than a younger client. These results are of significant importance to NMB Bank to focus strategically on saving youth in the district, who constitute 50% of the population.

Conclusion

This study examined the factors influencing the adoption of the NMB Mkononi service in the Kongwa district, Dodoma. The results provide insights into different facets of e-banking adoption, offering important perspectives on the levels of awareness and the factors that influence the adoption of this technology. Findings from the descriptive analysis indicated that while a significant portion of customers in the district are aware of the NMB Mkononi technology and possess basic phones, only a small number actively use mobile banking on their smartphones. The results of influencing factors showed that education has a significant positive contribution on the adoption of NMB Mkononi, indicating that participants with higher education were more likely to adopt the technology as compared to their counterparts. Income and network reliability indicated a positive statistically significant on the customers' decision to adopt NMB Mkononi. This implies that the higher the income, the more likely the consumer could adopt the mobile banking technology. The overall finding is that individuals with higher income and education, combined with good access to networks, view the adoption of NMB Mkononi positively. Moreover, it was determined that younger clients were more likely to utilize the technology than older individuals, as young people are generally more adept with modern technologies, making it easier to engage with them.

Recommendations and Implications

Considering these findings, it is recommended that the management of NMB Bank Plc and other financial institutions, as well as policymakers, should formulate strategies aiming to promote the use of digital financial services in rural and underserved segments in the region. Similarly, to facilitate a wider adoption of e-banking, initiatives should concentrate not only on enhancing technological aspects but also on tackling the diverse socioeconomic factors identified in this study. Ultimately, grasping the elements that influence adoption is vital for forming effective strategies that promote the use of e-banking services, thereby aiding financial inclusion and empowering individuals and communities.

This research carries various policy and practical considerations for governments, policymakers, and banking leaders. The findings from this study highlighted the importance of clients' socio-demographic characteristics in the uptake of mobile banking services. These findings signal to bank managers and government officials the need to enhance and refine their marketing strategies to boost awareness and outreach efforts among a larger user base, particularly in rural locations. Additionally, it was noted that education and income significantly influence the adoption of NMB Mkononi, as they provide greater capability and confidence in navigating new technology. This, therefore, necessitates that bank managers and policymakers invest more resources into educating customers about the benefits of mobile banking technology. This approach will assist banks in increasing the number of customers who are willing to use mobile banking services.

The current study has made important contributions to the literature on the determinants of mobile banking adoption in the banking industry. In the first instance, the study has shown the relevance of socio-demographic characteristics such as age, education, and income in explaining the adoption of new technologies in the context of sub-Saharan Africa, especially in Tanzania. Secondly, it adds and contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the adoption of mobile banking in the context of Less Developed countries (LDCs) like Tanzania. Also, combining TAM and ECM theories added more knowledge in explaining the users' continuance intention to use mobile-banking technology both in the pre- and post-adoption era.

Limitation and Future Research

Only cross-sectional data were employed in this study in making the conclusion, which limits the long-term understanding of the key factors affecting the adoption of mobile banking technology. In this respect, future studies should consider using time series data to capture both short- and long-term effects. This will help the government and financial service provider to formulate policy and strategy that encourage technology adoption. Future studies should also expand the coverage of the study area to include more districts in Tanzania.

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